

Methodology for developing the sports form of middle-distance runners in the third year of the training stage

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of data obtained from implementing a methodology for the phased application of a training program aimed at developing the sports form of middle-distance runners in the 3rd year of the training stage.

Methods: The following were used as examples of pedagogical tests and control exercises: analysis of scientific and methodological literature, pedagogical observation, organization of research, pedagogical experience, mathematical and statistical methods, and analysis of the obtained results.

Results: A general analysis of the main statistical characteristics of physical fitness indicators for 14-year-old middle-distance runners in the experimental and control groups at the training stage, based on results recorded at the beginning and end of the study. The tests included: 1 - 30-meter sprint time (sec); 2 - 60-meter sprint time (sec); 3 - 100-meter sprint time (sec); 4 - 200-meter sprint time (sec); 5 - 800-meter run time (sec); and 6 - Standing long jump (cm). The absolute difference (AF) was 17.84% in the experimental group (EG) and 8.79% in the control group (CG), while the relative difference (NF) was 23.94% in the EG and 11.96% in the CG. A significant difference was observed, which substantiates the effectiveness of the developed methodology.

Conclusion: The results of current research and pedagogical observations revealed that in the study conducted to determine the physical fitness of middle-distance runners, no significant difference was observed in the physical fitness level indicators between the experimental and control groups. However, when we analyzed and compared the results obtained at the beginning of this study, it was found that the athletic form of the athletes in both the experimental and control groups was not sufficiently developed.

Keywords: Preparatory training, competition period, physical training, cumulative effectiveness, means, athletic form, step-by-step improvement.

Introduction

Today, the geographical expansion of competition in track and field events and the continuous improvement of competition results necessitate constant enhancement of the athlete training system based on new technologies and effective programs [1, 2, 4].

One of the main reasons is the minimal consideration of factors influencing the

formation of middle-distance runners' athletic form during annual training sessions and its stability during competition periods [3, 5, 6].

In the third year of the training group, 936 hours of training load are planned and 14-year-old students are admitted. They should strengthen their health, improve general and special physical preparedness, perfect the technique and tactics of their chosen event, and know the competition rules. Research was conducted in these groups based on the 2-stage training methodology (see Tables 1 and 2).

Result and discussion

The main content in substantiating the effectiveness of this study is the special development and implementation in the training process of microcycles for the autumn-winter and spring-summer preparatory stages in the annual training cycle of middle-distance runners in the 3rd year of the training phase.

During the third year of the training stage, if an athlete shows good results in control and qualifying competitions but experiences a noticeable decrease in performance between main competitions, it indicates instability in their sports form.

We can consider an athlete to be in good sports form if they maintain their form during the competition period of the annual training cycle, sustain its stability during the main competition period, and improve upon their best results from previous competitions.

Comparing the speed dynamics of middle-distance running (800-1500 m) in various tactical scenarios, it can be noted that most top athletes increase their speed in the final 200-300 m, up to the last 100 m before the finish line. They work as quickly as possible by increasing stride frequency. In 800 and 1500 meter races, the second half of the distance should be covered with minimal deceleration.

In the program aimed at developing sports form for the third group of the training stage, the total training volume was 936

Table 1. Autumn-winter training mechanism of the 2-stage training program for middle-distance runners in the third year of the training phase

Microcycle type	General duration	Purpose	Tasks	Load duration	Intensity zone	Running distance	Rest interval	Organizational and Methodological Instructions
STAGE I								
Autumn-winter preparatory period (fundamental and pre-competition stage)								
Fundamental Preparation Stage								
Introductory	6-8 weeks	Establishing basic training	- Strengthening health; - Development of physical qualities.	WU: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	10-12 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active recovery and sports games according to the individual condition of athletes after training
				MT: 70-80 min.	151-165 bpm.			
				CD: 10-15 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Extensive	6-8 weeks	Development of basic training	- Increasing physical fitness.	WU: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active recovery and sports games according to the individual condition of athletes after training
				MT: 50-60 min.	151-165 bpm.			
				CD: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Developmental	6-8 weeks	Improvement of basic training	- Development of functional training; - Formation of special fitness.	WU: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	6-8 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active recovery and sports games according to the individual condition of athletes after training
				MT: 50-60 min.	151-170 bpm.			
				CD: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Autumn-Winter pre-competition preparation stage								
Intensive	4 weeks	Development of integrated preparation for competitions	- Development of maximum speed endurance; - Increasing technical-tactical training.	WU: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	4-5 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active recovery and sports games according to the individual condition of athletes after training
				MT: 50-60 min.	151-175 bpm.			
				CD: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Pre-competition	4 weeks	Development of integrated preparation for competitions	- Development of maximum speed endurance; - Increasing technical-tactical training.	WU: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	4-5 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active recovery and sports games tailored to individual athletes' conditions after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-175 bpm			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm			
Autumn-winter competition period								
Competition	2 weeks	Ensuring athletes' successful participation in competitions	- Demonstrating a high level of integrated preparation; - Developing special endurance; - Reaching peak physical condition and transforming it into high performance.	TQ: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm	3 km	Hard (partial) rest	Active recovery and sports games tailored to individual athletes' conditions after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-170 bpm			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm			
Intensive	1 week	Ensuring athletes' successful participation in competitions	- Demonstrating a high level of integrated preparation; - Developing special endurance; - Reaching peak physical condition and transforming it into high performance.	TQ: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm	3 km	Hard (partial) rest	Active recovery and sports games tailored to individual athlete's conditions after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-175 bpm			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm			
Maintenance	1 week	Ensuring athletes' successful participation in competitions	- Demonstrating a high level of integrated preparation; - Developing special endurance; - Reaching peak physical condition and transforming it into high performance.	TQ: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm	4 km	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games tailored to individual athlete's condition after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-165 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Transition period								
Recovery	4 weeks	Athletes' recovery	- Use of effective methods for body recovery; - Maintaining the athlete's work capacity and ensuring active rest.	TQ: 15-20 min.	131-140 bpm.	3 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games tailored to individual athlete's condition after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	141-150 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Transition	4 weeks	Athletes' recovery	- Use of effective methods for body recovery; - Maintaining the athlete's work capacity and ensuring active rest.	TQ: 15-20 min.	131-140 bpm.	3 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games tailored to individual athlete's condition after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	141-150 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			

Table 1. Knowledge and skills to be acquired within the program for developing athletes' knowledge and skills on ethical and legal rules

Microcycle type	Total duration	Purpose	Tasks	Load volume	Intensity zone	Running distance	Rest interval	Organizational and methodological instructions
STAGE II								
Spring-summer preparatory period (fundamental and pre-competition stage)								
Fundamental preparation stage								
Buildup	2 weeks	Establishing basic training	- Strengthening health; - Developing physical qualities.	PP: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games for athletes after training, based on their individual condition
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-165 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
High-volume	2 weeks	Developing basic training	- Increasing physical fitness.	TQ: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games for athletes after training, based on their individual condition
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-165 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Developmental	2 weeks	Improving basic training	- Developing physical fitness; - Forming special fitness.	PP: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games for athletes after training, based on their individual condition
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-170 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Spring-summer pre-competition preparatory stage								
Intense	2 weeks	Developing integrated preparation for competitions	- Developing competitive-specific qualities; - Increasing technical-tactical training.	PP: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games for athletes after training, based on their individual condition
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-175 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Pre-competition	2 weeks	Developing integrated preparation for competitions	- Developing competitive-specific qualities; - Increasing technical-tactical training.	PP: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games tailored to the individual state of athletes after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-175 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Spring-summer competition period								
Competition	2 weeks	Ensuring successful participation of athletes in competitions	- Demonstrating a high level of integrated preparation; - Developing special endurance; - Achieving peak physical condition and transforming it into high results.	PP: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games tailored to the individual state of athletes after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-170 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Intensive	2 weeks	Ensuring successful participation of athletes in competitions	- Demonstrating a high level of integrated preparation; - Developing special endurance; - Achieving peak physical condition and transforming it into high results.	PP: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games tailored to the individual state of athletes after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	151-175 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Transition period								
Recovery	1 week	Athletes' recovery	- Employing effective means of body recovery; - Maintaining the athlete's work capacity and ensuring active rest.	PP: 15-20 min.	131-140 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Active rest and sports games tailored to the individual state of athletes after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	141-150 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Transition	1 week	Recovery of athletes' bodies	- Application of effective means for body recovery; - Maintaining the athlete's work capacity and ensuring active rest.	PP: 15-20 min.	131-140 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Use of active rest and sports games based on the individual condition of athletes after training
				MAIN PART: 50-60 min.	141-150 bpm.			
				FINAL PART: 5-10 min.	88-94 bpm.			
Summer-Autumn Transition Stage								
Transition-Entry	2 weeks	Recovery of athletes' bodies	- Application of effective means for body recovery; - Maintaining the athlete's work capacity and ensuring active rest.	PP: 15-20 min.	141-150 bpm.	8-10 km.	Hard (partial) rest	Use of active rest and sports games based on the individual condition of athletes after training

Fig 1. Program (methodology) aimed at developing sports form in group 3 of the training stage

Table 1. Analysis of changes in the main statistical characteristics of physical fitness indicators of 14-year-old middle-distance runners at the training stage during the study

No.	Control tests	Groups	Beginning of the experiment			End of experiment			Test reliability indicators			
			X	σ	V, %	X	σ	V, %	AAD	RG	t	P
1	30m Run (sec.)	EG	6.83	1.09	15.96	5.36	0.81	15.11	1.47	21.52	3.75	<0.01
		CG	6.68	1.04	15.61	5.97	0.92	15.48	0.71	10.63	1.77	>0.05
2	60m Run (sec.)	EG	12.92	2.20	16.99	9.72	1.57	16.15	3.20	24.77	4.11	<0.001
		CG	12.74	2.11	16.59	11.08	1.72	15.50	1.66	13.03	2.11	<0.05
3	100m Run (sec.)	EG	14.93	2.24	14.98	11.56	1.63	14.10	3.37	22.57	4.22	<0.001
		CG	14.82	2.17	14.62	13.06	1.90	14.51	1.76	11.88	2.12	<0.05
4	200m Run (sec.)	EG	31.15	5.29	16.97	24.04	3.88	16.14	7.11	22.83	3.76	<0.01
		CG	31.69	5.26	16.60	28.12	4.64	16.49	3.57	11.27	1.76	>0.05
5	800m Run (sec.)	EG	201.46	32.21	15.99	158.05	23.92	15.13	43.41	21.55	3.75	<0.01
		CG	206.29	32.21	15.61	184.51	28.61	15.51	21.78	10.56	1.75	>0.05
6	Standing Long Jump (cm)	EG	159.35	25.44	15.96	207.82	31.44	15.13	48.47	30.42	4.15	<0.001
		CG	161.39	25.21	15.62	184.67	28.63	15.50	23.28	14.42	2.11	<0.05
Average growth			EG			17.84			23.94			
			CG			8.79			11.96			

Note: General analysis of the main statistical characteristics of physical fitness indicators for 14-year-old middle-distance runners in the experimental and control groups at the training stage, based on the results recorded at the beginning and end of the study: AF-absolute difference for EG 17.84 % and CG 8.79 % NF-relative difference for EG 23.94% and CG 11.96% A significant difference was observed, which substantiates the high effectiveness of the developed methodology.

km/100%: aerobic loads 702 km/75%, mixed loads 187.2 km/20%, anaerobic loads 32.76 km/3.5%, jumps 14.04 km/1.5%, games 100 hours, and special strength exercises 20 hours.

These were allocated and incorporated into the training process (see Figure 1). The analysis of the results obtained during the study is also presented in Table.

Facilities, halls, equipment), a system for selecting and supporting talented athletes, financing and sponsorship, as well as the activities of sports federations and governing bodies.

From the standpoint of moral standards, the organizational culture within a team or national team is of particular importance. If the values of "clean sport," fair competition, and absolute intolerance towards doping are established at the management level, athletes will also feel the responsibility to adhere to these principles.

Organizational measures also include internal control mechanisms: implementation of collective codes of conduct, verification of the professional reputation of involved specialists, and monitoring of training loads and recovery methods.

General analysis of the main statistical characteristics of physical fitness indicators for 14-year-old middle-distance runners in the experimental and control groups at the training stage, based on the results recorded at the beginning and end of the study: 1-30 meter run time (sec.); 2-60 meter run time (sec.); 3-100 meter run time (sec.); 4-200 meter run time (sec.); 5-800 meter run time (sec.) and 6- Standing long jump (cm) tests showed an AF-absolute difference of 17.84% for EG and 8.79% for CG, NF-relative difference of 23.94% for EG and 11.96% for CG. A significant difference was observed, which substantiates the effectiveness of the developed methodology (see Table 3).

Our research, conducted through the phased application of microcycle loads planned for the annual training of middle-distance runners, involved traction, volume, developmental, special pre-competition, and winter competition microcycles. The analysis and synthesis of the obtained data allowed us to substantiate that we achieved the expected effectiveness from the study.

Conclusion

The effectiveness of implementing the methodology for the phased application of the training program aimed at developing the sports form of middle-distance runners in the 3rd year of the training phase, under the influence of the developed training methodology, was $P < 0.001$. Based on this data and the results of pedagogical research, we can conclude that in maintaining the sports form of middle-distance runners during the competitive period of annual training sessions, it is recommended to approach it by taking into account the specifics of the sport and the qualifications of the athletes.

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